

On the relevance of grasp metrics for predicting grasp success

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Abstract—We aim to reliably predict whether a grasp on a known object is successful before it is executed in the real world. There is an entire suite of grasp metrics that has already been developed which rely on precisely known contact points between object and hand. However, it remains unclear whether and how they may be combined into a general purpose grasp stability predictor. In this paper, we analyze these questions by leveraging a large scale database of simulated grasps on a wide variety of objects. For each grasp, we compute the value of seven metrics. Each grasp is annotated by human subjects with ground truth stability labels. Given this data set, we train several classification methods to find out whether there is some underlying, non-trivial structure in the data that is difficult to model manually but can be learned. Quantitative and qualitative results show the complexity of the prediction problem. We found that a good prediction performance critically depends on using a combination of metrics as input features. Furthermore, non-parametric and non-linear classifiers best capture the structure in the data.

I. INTRODUCTION

An open problem in autonomous robotic manipulation is the prediction of grasp success *before* executing it in the real world. This is especially the case for precision grasps. They are characterized by few contact points between hand and object which makes them more brittle than power grasps.

Many analytic metrics have been developed to reliably predict precision grasp success. They usually assume known object and robot hand models along with their relative pose to compute precise contact points between object and hand. Some of these metrics have been carefully evaluated by comparing their prediction with the outcome of real robot experiments [1, 2]. The results of these studies showed that the most popular grasp metrics are not very good predictors of grasp success in the real world. This insight lead to the development of data driven techniques for finding metrics to predict grasp success even for the cases where significant uncertainty is introduced through unknown object shape, uncertain object pose estimation and inaccurate actuation (see [3] for an extensive review).

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Fig. 1: Examples of *Stable* (top row) and *Unstable* (bottom row) grasps.

Data-driven approaches require ground truth annotations of grasp success of the kind shown in Fig. 1. One way to generate these annotations is to execute grasps with a real robot through an existing grasp strategy and observing their outcome.

For instance, Levine et al. [4], Pinto et al. [5] approach the objects always from the top using a simple gripper. Detry et al. [6] sample not only top grasps but consider all 6 DoF for generating grasp candidates. In other approaches, humans demonstrate a grasp to the robot [1, 7, 8] or manually label images of objects with good grasps [9, 10]. All of these approaches are expensive, tedious and may require an entire robot farm [4] to sample sufficiently many annotated data points.

Another possibility is to execute and automatically label grasp candidates in simulation [11, 12, 13]. This way, several hundred thousand data points can be generated without any manual labeling or time-consuming execution in the real world. However, this leads to a *chicken-and-egg* situation: We want automatically label training data for the purpose of learning more informative grasp metrics. However, existing metrics do not lend themselves well to the automatic labeling task [1, 2]. Kappler et al. [11] propose to use physics simulation for this purpose. By comparing to the answers of a human oracle, the authors show how this leads to more realistic labels than when using a classic grasp stability metric. However, a full physics simulation is orders of magnitude more expensive than to compute the classic grasp metrics.

In this paper, we analyze how well seven different,

commonly-used grasp metrics [14, 15] are able to predict grasp success; either individually or in combination. We hypothesize that these metrics capture different aspects of precision grasp stability and thereby have different biases and generalization characteristics.

We use the human labeled data from [11] to perform this analysis. In contrast to the aforementioned real-world datasets, [11] contains the ground truth necessary for grasp metric computation. Our aim is to find a classifier that takes one or all of these metrics as input and outputs a binary success label. We test a set of classification methods that covers different potential characteristics of the function of interest (linear versus non-linear; parametric versus non-parametric). In this way we aim to understand the underlying structure of the data and whether these seven commonly used metrics are expressive enough.

The contributions of this paper are: (i) we analyze classic grasp metrics given a much larger data set of human annotations (4699) on a much larger variation of objects (616) than previous studies; (ii) we use a wide set of classification methods to analyze the underlying structure of the function mapping; and (iii) we quantitatively and qualitatively compare the outcome of our analysis with previous similar studies [14, 15, 7, 11].

In our experiments, we show that a good prediction performance critically depends on using a combination of grasp metrics as input features. We also show that non-parametric, non-linear methods can best capture the underlying structure in the data.

II. FOUNDATIONS AND RELATED WORK

A. Grasps Database

There are several publicly-available databases that contain grasps with ground truth annotations [5, 4, 9, 12, 7]. However, only [12, 11, 7] include the ground truth object models and relative pose between hand and object. This is necessary to compute the classic grasp metrics which we study in this paper.

In some databases, ground truth labels of grasp success are generated by executing grasps in the real world [5, 4, 7]. These are much more informative labels than can be generated by human subjects just looking at pictures of grasps. However, they are also much more time-consuming and expensive to generate. Consequently, the resulting data sets are often much smaller than data sets generated in simulation or may require an entire robot farm [4] to generate sufficiently many grasps.

In previous work, Kappler et al. [11] generated a large-scale grasp database on a wide variety of objects in simulation using OpenRave [16]. The grasps are generated by sampling grasp candidates uniformly around the object surface; thereby introducing less bias. In total, it contains approximately half a million grasps generated on more than 600 different object models with the BarrettHand.

Kappler et al. [11] aimed at automatically generating training data with ground truth labels of grasp stability. The authors assumed that human subjects are perfect oracles for

this prediction task and their judgement could therefore be used to validate the proposed automatic labeling process. Therefore, a subset of the grasps from the database were presented to human subjects using *Amazon Mechanical Turk* (AMT). They labeled them as either *Stable*, *Unstable* or *Unknown*. Each grasp was judged by at least 5 different subjects. The final label per grasp was averaged over their responses to normalize for the remaining noise.

In this paper, we are using this extensive database as a basis to analyze an entire suite of grasp metrics (Section II-C) and whether they are useful by themselves or in combination to predict grasp stability. As a ground truth label of this data, we will use the human labels, only for *Stable* and *Unstable* grasps. The database is the only one that has *human* grasp annotation for a *large* set of grasps (4752) and applied to a wide variety of different objects (616) with a known 3D shape model. It also considers *noise* in the object pose for each reference grasp.

B. A Physics Metric

The central hypothesis by Kappler et al. [11] is that physical forward simulation of grasps is more suitable for automatic labeling of data than the classical and most common Ferrari & Canny metric [18]. The final labels are computed by averaging over the physically-simulated outcomes of 20 grasps on a slightly perturbed object pose around a reference pose. This mimics noise in perception and actuation of a robot.

The hypothesis is tested against the answers of human subjects on a subset of the generated grasps. The results show that the labels based on the physics simulation are more realistic and therefore more suitable to learn from. However, it is also orders of magnitudes more expensive to compute than the classic metrics.

For reference, we also report this metric in the result section. It indicates the prediction performance of grasp stability that can be achieved when investing into this computationally expensive physics simulation.

C. Characterization of Quality Metrics

Leon et al. [14] and Rubert et al. [15] performed a statistical analysis of the values produced by ten selected quality metrics on a database that included grasps for seven different hands and more than hundred objects, resulting in around 200.000 different grasp configurations. The analysis is performed exclusively in simulation and consisted in establishing upper and lower thresholds for the normalization of the metrics; measuring the stability of the metrics in the presence of small disturbances; and more importantly, visualizing the correlation between different metrics. This last result allowed to discard three metrics reducing the initial set to seven. These are the seven independent metrics which will be used in this paper, see Table I.

The results of these works offer numerical and practical information about the use of the metrics. The main motivation of this paper is to address the limitation of Leon et al. [14], Rubert et al. [15] that no relation between highly ranked

grasp and the success of their execution is presented. The human labels from [11] provide a valuable ground truth to fulfill this purpose.

TABLE I: Summary of the selected quality metrics

Name	Description	Formula
Q_{A1}	Smallest singular value of Grasp Matrix [19]	$\sigma_{min}(G)$
Q_{B1}	Distance between the centroid of the contact polygon and the object's centre of mass[20, 21]	$1 - \frac{distance(p, p_c)}{distance_{max}}$
Q_{B2}	Area of the grasp polygon[22]	$\frac{Area(Polygon(p_1, p_2 \dots p_n))}{Area_{max}}$
Q_{B3}	Shape of the grasp polygon[23]	$1 - \frac{1}{\theta_{max}} \sum_{i=1}^{n_f} \theta_i - \bar{\theta} $
Q_{C2}	Volume of the convex hull[24]	$Volume(CW)/Volume_{max}$
Q_{D1}	Posture of hand finger joints[25]	$1 - \frac{1}{n_q} \sum_{i=1}^{n_q} (\frac{y_i - a_i}{a_i - y_{iM}})^2$
Q_{D2}	Inverse of the condition number of G_J [26, 27]	$\frac{\sigma_{min}(G_J)}{\sigma_{max}(G_J)}$

D. Related work

Goins et al. [7] present very relevant work to this paper. The authors address the problem of learning a predictor for successful grasps. In their approach, candidate grasps are instructed by humans and tested on a real robot. Up to 13 metrics are calculated for each grasp. Dimensionality reduction and a Gaussian Process are used to produce a predictor that demonstrates better performance than when using individual metrics.

There are similarities with our approach but there are also relevant differences. First of all, we are using 7 metrics instead of 13, but our subset has been previously reduced by discarding highly correlated metrics [15]. Although the classifiers may be able to cope with 13 metrics, we simplify the learning problem and the subsequent analysis by reducing the dimensionality of the input space. An obvious strength of [7] is that grasps are tested on a real robot, which is a more valuable ground-truth. However, all of these grasps have been demonstrated by humans. In our opinion, this introduces a bias in the selection of grasps that could affect the learned models. This process potentially discards grasp configurations which could be successful but are not intuitive for humans. Furthermore, the dataset is much smaller than the dataset used in this paper. Also fewer objects are considered.

III. METHODOLOGY

We aim to find a model $y = f(\mathbf{x}; \mathbf{w})$ that can predict binary grasp success y given an input feature vector \mathbf{x} consisting of seven grasp quality metrics. Our approach is to learn a binary classifier from the data in [11] that ideally minimizes the following equation:

$$\min_{\mathbf{w}} \sum_{(\mathbf{x}, y) \in \mathcal{D}} 1 - 1(f(\mathbf{x}; \mathbf{w}), y) \quad (1)$$

where \mathbf{w} denotes the parameter vector of the classifier and

$$1(f(\mathbf{x}; \mathbf{w}), y) = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } f(\mathbf{x}; \mathbf{w}) = y \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

Every classifier considered in this paper minimizes a loss in this setting. For various reasons, the exact loss formulations may vary per method, e.g. through different regularizers or by dropping the indicator function in order to get gradients. In the following, we first describe the input features and the output label. Then we briefly describe each classification method to have a self contained description. A more in-depth description of the classification methods used in this paper can be found in [29].

A. Feature Vector and Label

We compute the input feature vector \mathbf{x} for each grasp in [11] with OpenHand [30], a toolkit based on the OpenRave framework [16]. It provides a python library with different quality metrics (see Table I). Most of these metrics use the contact point information provided by the simulator, along with different information about the object and gripper geometry. The implementation and details of the quality metrics used in this paper is widely discussed in the literature Roa and Suárez [28], Leon et al. [14], Rubert et al. [15].

For contact detection, we use ODE. The friction coefficient of the contact points is 0.4. Each grasp has a ground truth success label provided by a human oracle where $y = 1$ refers to a *Stable* and $y = 0$ to an *Unstable* grasp. Our data set \mathcal{D} is comprised of tuples (\mathbf{x}, y) , a feature vector and the corresponding label.

B. Classification Methods

Given this data set \mathcal{D} , we train the following classifiers that have different characteristics (linear versus non-linear, non-parametric versus parametric) using SciKit-Learn [31] or Matlab [33]. The optimization for each method was done using grid search and cross-validation. Details are presented in each section.

1) *Logistic Regression*: Logistic regression is a linear model for classification. The logistic function $\sigma(\mathbf{w}^T \mathbf{x})$ models the probability $P(y = 1 | \mathbf{x})$ of feature vector \mathbf{x} describing a stable grasp $y = 1$ with

$$\sigma(a) = 1 / (1 + \exp(-a)). \quad (3)$$

To find the weight vector \mathbf{w} , we optimize the following regularized loss function:

$$\min_{\mathbf{w}} \|\mathbf{w}\|_1 - C \sum_{(\mathbf{x}, y) \in \mathcal{D}} y \ln t + (1 - y) \ln(1 - t) \quad \text{with} \quad (4)$$

with $t = \sigma(\mathbf{w}^T \mathbf{x})$, $\|\cdot\|_1$ denotes the L1-norm and encourages a sparse weight vector. C balances between the classification loss and the regularizer. The key assumption in logistic regression is linearity between the input features and the log odds, i.e. the log of ratios of binary class probability. If the data is linearly separable this method can recover the global minima of (1). We optimized the parameters using two loss functions ($L1$ and $L2$) and two values for C : [1,2]. The loss functions $L1$ and $C = 1$ showed the best performance.

2) *Naive Bayes*: Naive Bayes models the probability of a grasp being either stable or not using Bayes theorem. Its key assumption is that given the class label y , the distributions of the input variables $\mathbf{x} = (x_1, \dots, x_7)^T$ are independent. Thus, we can rewrite Bayes theorem as:

$$P(y | x_1, \dots, x_7) = \frac{P(y) \prod_{i=1}^7 P(x_i | y)}{P(x_1, \dots, x_7)} \quad (5)$$

To finally classify a data point, we have

$$f(\mathbf{x}; \mathbf{w}) = \hat{y} = \arg \max_y P(y) \prod_{i=1}^7 P(x_i | y) \quad (6)$$

The parameters of this Naive Bayes model are $P(y)$ (the relative frequency of class y in the training set) and $P(x_i | y)$ (the distribution of a grasp quality metric given a class label; modeled as Gaussian in this paper). We use *Maximum A Posteriori* (MAP) estimation to determine these parameters.

3) *K-Nearest Neighbors*: *K-Nearest Neighbors* (KNN) is a non-parametric approach. It makes no assumptions about the distribution that generates the data. Instead, it classifies a test data point based on the class membership of its K nearest neighbors in feature space. To define distances, we assume that this space is Euclidean.

Formally, KNN uses Bayes theorem to model the posterior probability of a grasp being successful or not

$$P(y = c | \mathbf{x}) = K_c / K \quad (7)$$

where K_c is the number of data points belonging to class c among the K nearest neighbors of \mathbf{x} and c corresponds to either *Stable* or *Unstable*. To classify a data point, we maximize this posterior distribution over the binary class labels.

K is the hyperparameter in this classification method. In general a larger K suppresses the effects of noise, but makes the classification boundaries less distinct. We used a validation set to find the optimal K for our data set. KNN is well suited for our relatively low-dimensional feature space. However, in its most basic form inference for this method does not scale well with the number of data points and dimension of feature space.

Two different weight functions were compared during the training: *uniform* and *distance*. The K value was analyzed from 1 to 20. In our results the *distance* function showed a better performance with a K value of 5.

4) *Classification Trees*: *Classification Trees* (CTs) are another non-parametric approach. A CT is a binary tree that divides the input feature space at each node j into two regions according to whether $x_i \leq \theta_j$ or $x_i > \theta_j$. θ_j is a parameter of the model. These sub-regions are independently subdivided further by moving down in the tree until a leaf node is reached.

Each leaf node of the tree encodes a region \mathcal{R}_τ in the input space. This region contains N_τ training data points associated with class labels y_n . Let us assume that a test data point with features \mathbf{x} ended up in the leaf node corresponding

to \mathcal{R}_τ . The probability $P(y = c | \mathbf{x})$ is then the fraction of data points labeled with c in that region. For the final classification of a test data point, we again maximize $P(y = c | \mathbf{x})$ over the class labels c .

To learn a CT, we need to find the optimal split parameters θ_j at each node of the tree. This is done by a standard greedy strategy where at each new node, we optimize a certain criteria over a set \mathcal{S} of candidate pairs of input features x_i and thresholds θ_j . The criteria has to capture the purity of class labels within the sub-region \mathcal{R}_τ resulting from a candidate split of the input region. In this paper, we chose the Gini impurity $g(\mathcal{R}_\tau)$:

$$\min_{s_\tau \in \mathcal{S}} g(\mathcal{R}_\tau) \text{ with } g(\mathcal{R}_\tau) = 1 - \sum_{c \in \{0,1\}} m_{c,\tau}^2 \quad (8)$$

The more nodes are added, the deeper the tree and therefore also the more complex the decision rule. To avoid overfitting, we have found a maximum tree *depth* = 5 using the validation set. We have further investigated using entropy as an impurity measure with no significant difference in the results.

5) *Support Vector Machines*: In this paper, we use Radial Basis Function *Support Vector Machines* (RBF SVMs) as a non-probabilistic binary classifier. It is characterized by defining a max-margin hyperplane that separates the two classes such that the distance between the closest data point and the hyperplane is maximized. Given a data point with \mathbf{x} as feature vector, we classify it as 1 if $f(\mathbf{x}; \mathbf{w}) > 0$ or 0 otherwise

To find the optimal parameters \mathbf{w} and b of the classifier given the dataset, we maximize the dual problem formulation

$$\max_{\alpha} \sum_{i=1}^{\|\mathcal{D}\|} \alpha_i - \sum_{i=1}^{\|\mathcal{D}\|} \sum_{j=1}^{\|\mathcal{D}\|} y_i \alpha_i k(\mathbf{x}_i, \mathbf{x}_j) y_j \alpha_j \quad (9)$$

$$\text{st. } \sum_{i=1}^{\|\mathcal{D}\|} \alpha_i y_i = 0 \text{ and } 0 \leq \alpha_i \leq C \quad (10)$$

where C trades off between margin size and correct classification of the data points and $k(\mathbf{x}_i, \mathbf{x}_j) = \exp(-\gamma \|\mathbf{x}_i - \mathbf{x}_j\|^2)$ is the RBF kernel with the hyperparameter γ . The hinge loss defines a soft margin that is beneficial in case the data is not separable but otherwise reduces to the hard margin SVM. In order to infer the class label we replace $f(\mathbf{x}; \mathbf{w})$ with the result of the dual optimization problem, $f(\mathbf{x}; \alpha) = \sum_{\alpha_i: \alpha_i > 0} \alpha_i k(\mathbf{x}_i, \mathbf{x}) + b$. Here the weight is determined based on the kernel evaluation and the dual variable.

6) *Gaussian Processes*: A *Gaussian Process* (GP) is a probabilistic, non-parametric method. More specifically, it is defined as a collection of a finite number of random variables with a joint Gaussian distribution. In our case, this collection consists of the grasps in the training data $\mathcal{D} = \{\mathbf{x}, y\}_{\|\mathcal{D}\|}$. In the following, we summarize the data in the matrix \mathbf{X} and vector \mathbf{y} . A GP can be seen as a distribution over functions with a mean μ and covariance Σ . The entries of the covariance matrix $K(\mathbf{X}, \mathbf{X})_{p,q}$ at row p and column q are defined based on a covariance function $k(\mathbf{x}_p, \mathbf{x}_q)$ with

some hyperparameters θ . We use the squared exponential covariance function

$$k(\mathbf{x}_p, \mathbf{x}_q) = \sigma_l^2 \exp(-((\mathbf{x}_p - \mathbf{x}_q)^T L^{-1}(\mathbf{x}_p - \mathbf{x}_q))/2) \quad (11)$$

where the hyperparameters are σ_l , the signal variance, and L , the identity matrix multiplied with the length scale l . We optimize these hyperparameters in the standard way by maximizing the marginal likelihood. To compute $P(y_0 = c|\mathbf{x}_0)$, we squash $f(\mathbf{x}_0)$ through the logit function (3).

7) *Neural Networks*: Neural networks are nonlinear functions that we use in this paper to map from our input feature vector \mathbf{x} to the binary labels y . They are organized in multiple layers. Except from the input layer, each layer takes the output of the previous layer as input, potentially transformed with some non-linear function. For a binary classification, the output of the last layer is transformed using the logistic function (3). To classify a test data point with for instance a two-layer network, we need to compute

$$P(y = c|\mathbf{x}) = \sigma \left(\sum_j w_{c_j}^{(2)} h \left(\sum_i w_{ji}^{(1)} x_i \right) \right) \quad (12)$$

where $h(\cdot)$ refer to the logsig transfer function of the output from the first layer. The superscript (1) and (2) indicates the different weights of each layer.

Up to 12 different algorithms and 100 hidden layers for training the *Neural Network* were tested using the MATLAB toolbox[33]. The best one was Bayesian Regularization [34], with layer size 17. It relies on the Levenberg-Marquardt algorithm to learn the optimal weights $\mathbf{w}^{(l)}$ for each layer. The validation set is used for early stopping and manual network structure optimization.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

We aim to find a model that predicts grasp success given an input feature vector of seven grasp metrics. Our approach is to learn this model from a large scale dataset with human annotations. In this section, we present results from two sets of experiments. First, we compare different classification methods to analyze their predictive capability. Second, we analyze the relevance of each grasp metric.

A. Dataset

The *null error rate* of the dataset is 57%. This rate measures the accuracy of a classifier that would label all grasps in the dataset as *Unstable*. We use this as a lower baseline to study the effectiveness of the different predictors.

The dataset of grasps is split in the two following ways. First, we perform a *random* split where the *Train* set contains 80% and the *Test* set 20% of the grasps.

Second, we split the dataset such that the *Train* set only contains grasps from 80% of the objects and the *Test* set grasps from the remaining 20%. In this way, the trained models will be tested on a set of *held-out objects* they have not previously seen.

B. Training, Validation and Testing

For both split methods (random and *held-out*) the *Train* dataset is used to perform a 10-fold cross-validation. This method splits the train dataset into 10 smaller subsets (folds). It trains 10 models, each using one of the folds for validation and the remaining folds for training. We report the *mean* classification accuracy and its standard deviation (*std*) over these 10 models. We optimized the hyperparameter of the classification methods using this 10-fold cross-validation. Once each classifier is cross validated, a new training is done using the *Train* dataset and the model's performance is tested on the *Test* set. The results of the cross-validation and testing are reported for the two types of data set splits: *random* and *held-out objects*. Results on the *held-out objects* are only shown for the comparison of the classification methods as scores remained similar to the *random* split in the second set of experiments.

C. Evaluation Metrics

For comparing the different classification methods in the first set of experiments, we report accuracy, precision, recall and F1 score. The accuracy score correspond to the count of correct predictions, i.e. the count of *true positives (tp)* and *true negatives*. The precision is the ratio $tp/(tp + fp)$ where fp is the number of false positives. Intuitively, it measures the ability of the classifier to avoid labeling a negative as a positive sample. The recall is the ratio $tp/(tp + fn)$ where fn the number of false negatives. Intuitively, recall measures the ability of a classifier to find all the positive samples. The F1 score is the harmonic mean of precision and recall: $F1 = 2 * (precision * recall)/(precision + recall)$. It reaches its maximum at 1 and minimum at 0.

D. Comparison of Classification methods

Table II presents the mean classification accuracy and its standard deviation per algorithm using cross-validation for the two different splits of the dataset. It also reports classification accuracy on the test sets.

TABLE II: Comparison of classification models. We report mean/std of classification accuracy using cross validation as well as accuracy on a test set. Results are computed for two dataset splits: random and held-out objects.

Classifier	Random Split		Held-out Objects	
	CrossVal	Test	CrossVal	Test
Logistic Regression	0.73±0.03	0.72	0.73±0.05	0.72
Naive Bayes	0.55±0.02	0.55	0.55±0.06	0.58
K-Nearest neighbors	0.80±0.02	0.78	0.76±0.02	0.74
Classification trees	0.80±0.01	0.78	0.75±0.01	0.72
SVM	0.70±0.02	0.70	0.69±0.07	0.70
Gaussian Process	0.75±0.03	0.75	0.74±0.04	0.76
Neural Networks	0.80±0.05	0.75	0.76±0.05	0.73

The results shown in this table are achieved with models whose hyperparameters are already optimized on a validation set.

A deeper analysis of the performance of different algorithm is shown in Table III. Additionally to the accuracy already reported in Table II, it also report precision, recall

and F1-score. As a reference, we also calculate these metrics for the binary labels generated through physics simulation of the grasps [11].

TABLE III: Comparison of classification methods using different metrics to evaluate models performance.

	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1-Score
Logistic Regression	0.72	0.75	0.72	0.72
Naive Bayes	0.55	0.73	0.55	0.50
K-Nearest Neighbors	0.78	0.77	0.77	0.77
Classification Trees	0.78	0.78	0.78	0.78
SVM	0.70	0.72	0.70	0.70
Gaussian Process	0.75	0.76	0.76	0.76
Neural Networks	0.75	0.75	0.75	0.75
Physics Metric	0.87	0.87	0.87	0.87

E. Quality Metrics Predictive Ability

In this second set of experiments, we analyze the performance of individual quality metrics to predict the stability of a grasp. This analysis is done in two ways, first a study on the individual performance of each metric and then, an ablation study on the influence of each metric for the predictors. To support this analysis, we visualize the distribution of *Stable/Unstable* grasps for each metric. Figure 2 shows the histograms of this data (with normal or log scale).

Given the results from the comparison of classification models, we selected Classification Trees and KNN to study the ability of individual quality metrics to predict grasp success. Table IV reports classification accuracy. Additionally, we analyzed the performance of these classifiers when they use as input features all but one of the quality metrics. Table V shows the results of this ablation analysis.

TABLE IV: Performance of individual Quality Metrics to predict grasp stability.

Selected Metric	Classification trees		K-Nearest neighbors	
	CrossVal	Test	CrossVal	Test
Q_{A1}	0.60 ± 0.03	0.62	0.61 ± 0.02	0.61
Q_{B1}	0.57 ± 0.00	0.59	0.57 ± 0.02	0.58
Q_{B2}	0.57 ± 0.00	0.59	0.57 ± 0.01	0.56
Q_{B3}	0.57 ± 0.00	0.59	0.63 ± 0.02	0.64
Q_{C2}	0.75 ± 0.03	0.72	0.73 ± 0.02	0.71
Q_{D1}	0.57 ± 0.00	0.59	0.57 ± 0.03	0.58
Q_{D2}	0.57 ± 0.00	0.59	0.57 ± 0.03	0.59

TABLE V: Ablation analysis on the use of Quality Metrics to predict the stability of grasps.

Discarded Metric	Classification trees		K-Nearest neighbors	
	CrossVal	Test	CrossVal	Test
Q_{A1}	0.73 ± 0.02	0.74	0.75 ± 0.02	0.76
Q_{B1}	0.74 ± 0.02	0.75	0.78 ± 0.02	0.76
Q_{B2}	0.74 ± 0.02	0.74	0.76 ± 0.02	0.77
Q_{B3}	0.72 ± 0.02	0.73	0.76 ± 0.03	0.80
Q_{C2}	0.69 ± 0.03	0.70	0.72 ± 0.02	0.72
Q_{D1}	0.74 ± 0.02	0.74	0.75 ± 0.02	0.76
Q_{D2}	0.74 ± 0.02	0.76	0.77 ± 0.02	0.77

Fig. 2: Distribution of *Stable* (green) and *Unstable* (red) grasps for individual quality metrics. Left) Histogram with linear scale of y-axis. Right) Histogram with log scale of y-axis.

V. DISCUSSION

In this work we have studied the reliability of different machine learning algorithms for predicting the stability of a

grasp. A database with more than 4699 grasps classified by humans as *Stable* or *Unstable* has been evaluated using the quality metrics listed in Table I. With this data, we analyzed the direct relation between independent *Quality Metrics* and the human-evaluated stability of the grasp.

Table II shows the results for the different learning models using the seven quality metrics. Four types of models obtain the best results (*K-Nearest neighbors*, *Classification trees*, *Gaussian Process* and *Neural Networks*). The column presenting results when the data is split by objects is a good indicator of the generalization capability of the models. Here, a *Gaussian Process* performs best. An additional comment comes from the comparison between the cross-validation performance on the training set and the performance on the test set. The values are close in general, indicating that overfitting is well controlled. In general, non-parametric and non-linear methods seem to capture the structure of the data best. As expected from Figure 2, assuming conditional independence of the input quality metrics (Naive Bayes) leads to the worst performance.

Table III reports similar results as Table II. Interestingly, this table also includes the performance of the *Physics Metric* [11] on the test dataset. It clearly outperforms the models learned using the combination of the other seven quality metrics, and as we show below the performance of any individual metric. The drawback is that this metric is based on a dynamic simulation and is computationally much more expensive than computing the grasp quality metrics. For real time grasp prediction, the computation of a few quality metrics will be always faster than dynamic simulation.

Between the four more successful models some practical considerations in terms of computational effort can be made. Especially, prediction time is of interest in this context. Except from *K-Nearest Neighbors* and *Gaussian Processes*, all classification methods scale well with an increasing number of training data points.

More interesting is the analysis of the contributions of each individual metric in the prediction. This is shown in Tables IV and V. Two main results can be observed. First, only metric Q_{C2} shows a clear discriminative capability (72% using *Classification trees*) while the remaining metrics remain at the *null error rate*, 57%, or slightly above. These results highlight the complexity of the classification problem. Evidence of this can be found in Figure 2 where, for each metric, the distribution of *Stable* and *Unstable* labels is represented. There is a strong overlap of these distributions making it hard to establish clearly differentiated clusters on any of the metrics

Second, however, when combined, the predictive capability of the quality metrics increases to 12% above *null error rate* in the worst case (70% when only discarding Q_{C2} in Table V). This suggests that the data is easier separable when represented in the combined space. This structure can be exploited by the classifiers (except by Naive Bayes).

To relate to results in similar papers [7], we also report the results from a *Gaussian Process* model in Table II. It shows

similar performance to other learned models. However, we cannot draw further conclusions as the dataset used in [7] is very different (in terms of size, features and labels) and the results are reported differently.

The evaluation through metrics lays in the ability to obtain accurate data from simulation, that will be noisy in real world. Although the robustness of metrics is studied in other works [15, 14], direct application of this results to real experiments should be taken carefully.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

This paper presents a study on the capability and relevance of quality metrics to predict the stability of a given grasp. A large database of human labeled samples has been employed to train several binary classifiers. The results have demonstrated the complexity of the problem but also that a combination of different metrics can deliver a performance up to 0.78; more than 0.20 over the *null error rate* and higher than any individual metric.

The contributions of the paper are therefore: we analyzed classic quality metrics on a database of 4699 human labeled samples, more than in any other study; a set of classification methods has been used and compared, showing which of them performs best; and, the results have been quantitatively and qualitatively compared with previous results.

There are several future directions. In the current data set, human subjects have judged the stability of a grasp by looking at pictures of it that are taken from different viewpoints. Although this allows a very large amount of labels, they have not been verified by executing the grasps on a real robot and checking the outcome. A further study with samples executed on real robots is necessary to confirm the results of this work. Two main questions should be addressed: *Do the results presented here translate to real robot executions?*, and *How good are humans as predictors of grasp success?*.

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